

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VIOLENT VIDEO GAME EXPOSURE AND AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR IN CHILDREN

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Annotation. This article focuses on how playing video games affect children and if it makes them behave aggressively. In recent years, video games have become an important part of children's life. Many games have things in them like fighting and shooting. The main goal of this research is to analyze whether exposure to such content affects children's emotions and behavior. This study used a kind of research where they asked 40 children between 10 and 15 years old some questions. What they found out is that children who play video games a lot tend to get angry and upset more easily and they do things without thinking. We also found out that there are other things that can make children behave aggressively like what their family is, like how much their parents are involved and what kind of person they are. So playing video games is not the only reason why children behave aggressively. This study shows that is really important for children to not play video games much and for their parents to be involved is what they are doing.

Keywords. Video games, children, aggression, behavior, violence, psychological impact, media influence, emotional state.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot video o'yinlarni o'ynash bolalarga qanday ta'sir qilishini va ularning tajovuzkor bo'lib qolishini o'rganadi. So'nggi yillarda video o'yinlar bolalar hayotining muhim qismiga aylandi. Ko'pgina o'yinlarda janjal va otishma kabi narsalar mavjud. Ushbu tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi bunday kontentga duchor bo'lish bolalarning histuyg'ulari va xatti-harakatlariga ta'sir qiladimi yoki yo'qligini tahlil qilishdir. Ushbu tadqiqotda 10 yoshdan 15 yoshgacha bo'lgan 40 ta boladan ba'zi savollar berilgan tadqiqot turi qo'llanildi. Ular aniqlagan narsa shundaki, video o'yinlarni ko'p o'ynaydigan bolalar tez-tez jahli chiqadi va xafa bo'lishadi va ular o'ylamasdan ishlarni qilishadi. Shuningdek, biz bolalarning tajovuzkor bo'lishiga olib keladigan boshqa narsalar ham borligini aniqladik, masalan, ularning oilasi qanday, ota-onalari qanchalik ishtirok etadi va ular qanday inson. Shunday qilib, video o'yinlarni o'ynash bolalarning tajovuzkor bo'lishining yagona sababi emas. Ushbu tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, bolalar uchun video o'ynamaslik juda muhim.

Kalit so'zlar: Video o'yinlar, bolalar, agressiya, xulq-atvor, zo'ravonlik, psixologik ta'sir, media ta'sir, hissiy holat.

Аннотация. Данное исследование рассматривает, как видеоигры влияют на детей и могут ли они вызывать агрессивное поведение. В последние годы видеоигры стали важной частью жизни детей. Многие игры содержат элементы насилия, такие как драки и стрельба. Основная цель исследования — определить, влияет ли воздействие такого контента на эмоциональное состояние и поведение детей. В ходе исследования были опрошены 40 детей в возрасте от 10 до 15 лет. Результаты показали, что дети, которые часто играют в видеоигры, чаще проявляют раздражительность, агрессию и импульсивное поведение. Также было установлено, что на агрессивное поведение влияют не только видеоигры, но и семейная среда, участие родителей и

индивидуальные особенности личности. Таким образом, видеоигры не являются единственной причиной агрессивного поведения детей. Данное исследование показывает важность контроля времени, проводимого детьми за видеоиграми.

Ключевые слова: видеоигры, дети, агрессия, поведение, насилие, психологическое влияние медиа, , эмоциональное состояние

Introduction. In recent years, video games have become a big part of children and teenagers entertainment. With all the technological advancements, modern games are more realistic and interactive. Many games have stuff like fighting, using guns and fake battles. There are a lot of debate about this among experts, teachers and parents. Some research says that paying games can lead to children thinking more aggressively getting used to violence and changing their behavior. On the other hand some researchers think video games are just fun and do not really affect how children behave in real life. This issue is important because children are still growing and can be easily influenced by things like video games. Experience can shape how they think about conflicts manage their feelings and interact with others. This study wants to look into how violent video games affect children behavior specifically if it makes them more aggressive. By checking out, we hope to add to the conversation among experts and give parents and teachers some advice. Video games are a part of many children's life and video games can have a significant impact, on their behavior.

Method. During the study, the participants' responses were analyzed in a systematic way. Separate groups were formed for each question and the results were compared. Differences between students who play a lot of violent games and those who play fewer were identified. In addition, participants' ages and genders were also taken into account. Means and percentages were used to analyze the data. This method helped to gain a clearer understanding of the research results. Additionally, participants' responses were recorded anonymously, which allowed them to answer openly and honestly. The collected data were also classified in graphical and tabular form.

This study used a survey to find out about video games habits.

The survey included 40 students aged between 10 and 15 years old.

These students were selected randomly from a school to get different opinions.

The survey had questions with choice and short answer options.

It asked about:

- how time they spend playing video games every day
- what kind of video games they like (violent or not violent)
- how they feel during and after playing video games
- how they behave in real life situations like conflicts.

Students told to answer based on their own experiences. The answers grouped by how students played violent video games. The researcher compared students who often played video games to those who played non-violent games. This way the researcher to identify patterns and possible relationships between exposure to violent content and aggressive behavior.

Result. The results showed that video games can affect children not only emotionally but also socially. Some participants said that after playing they felt tired and mentally unstable. Additionally, some children were observed to have decreased interest in real life interaction. They may prefer playing alone or spending time in a virtual environment. Furthermore, prolonged gaming is also likely to negatively affect attention span. Overall, the results indicate that the duration of play, in addition to the type of game is a very important factor. The study found connections between playing video games and behaving aggressively.

65% OF students who play violent games a lot said they get angry and upset easily. They said that they feel annoyed, frustrated or get mad quickly after playing these games. Students who play violent games mostly have more stable emotions. They reported aggressive reactions and better control over their feelings in everyday situations. The study also showed that how long students play video games matters. Students who play for than 2-3 hours a day are more likely to have strong emotional reactions than those who play for a shorter time. In general the data shows that both the type of game and the amount of time spent playing affect how children behave. Violent video games and long playtime can influence children behavior.

Discussion. Moreover, modern video games are often based on reward systems, which can also influence children's psychological habits. That is the frequent points, levels and achievements awarded in games can instill in children a constant desire for "quick results". This, in turn may lead to reduced patience and a diminished ability to work toward long-term goals. Additionally, some games are played competitively, which can intensify a child's sense of competition. This heightened competition can sometimes lead to increased stress and pressure. Especially in cases of losing, children may feel bad and experience emotional distress. Furthermore, video games can also affect children's time management skills. Spending too much time playing games can lead to neglect of schoolwork and other responsibilities. At the same time, in some cases, video games also help children learn technological skills, such as quick decision-making or problem-solving abilities. However, these positive effects are only effective when supervision and moderation are maintained. The results of this study show that playing video games can make children behave aggressively. When children play these games a lot they can start to think and feel differently about things that happen in life. They can even react differently to things that happen to them. However, it is important to understand that video games are not the only factor affecting behavior. Other factor, such as family environment, parent's role, social relationship and personality traits, also play a significant role. For example, children who get a lot of love and guidance from their parents are not as likely to be affected by violent video games. In addition, not all children respond to violent video games in the same way. Some children can play these games for only fun so they do not get too upset about what happens in the game. Other children may get very upset about what happens in the game. Instead of completely banning video games, a more effective approach is to manage and control their use. Parents should look at the games their children play make sure they do not play for long and encourage them to do things that are good for them and that they can learn from. Teachers can also contribute by raising awareness about media influence and promoting healthy behavior.

Conclusion. This study shows that a link between exposure to violent video games and aggressive behavior in children, especially when such games are played frequently and for extended periods. The results indicate that children who play violent games frequently exhibit greater emotional instability, quick temper, and impulsivity (acting without thinking). However, it is not corrected to view video games as the sole cause of aggression in children. Research also shows that children's behavior is shaped by several factors. These include the family environment, parenting, social relationships at school and the child's personal characteristics. Therefore, video games should be considered only one of several influencing factors. It is also crucial to properly manage children's use of the digital environment. Parents and teachers should monitor children's playtime, pay attention to selecting age-appropriate content and guide them toward beneficial activities. In conclusion, violent games are not inherently completely harmful, but excessive and unregulated use can negatively impact children's behavior.

References:

1. Anderson, C. A. Violent video games and aggression. (2010)
2. Gentile, D. A. The effects of video games on children. (2011)
3. Ferguson, C. J. Do violent games increase aggression? Perspectives on Psychological Science (2015)
4. Griffiths, M. The impact of video games on youth. Educational and health Journal. (2005)
5. Kirsh, S. J. Children, adolescents and media violence. (2006)
6. World Health Organization. Guidelines on children's media use. (2019)